

ON A CLASS OVERDETERMINED SYSTEMS OF SECOND-ORDER DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS WITH TWO INNER SINGULAR LINES

F.M.SHAMSUDINOV, R.S.VALIEV, AND A.H.DUNYA

ABSTRACT. This work discusses a system consisting of two differential equations: one is a linear hyperbolic equation of the second order with two internal singular lines, and the other is a first-order differential equation, also with two internal singular lines.

These equations are connected to each other through an unknown function. Relying on the methodology proposed in the works of N. Rajabov, the first equation of the system is represented as a product of two first-order differential operators. Introducing a new unknown function, the problem is reduced to solving two split first-order differential equations.

By solving them sequentially, it is possible to obtain a solution to the original second-order equation in the form of an expression containing two arbitrary functions of a single independent variable. Next, the second equation of the system is transformed into a special form, which simplifies further calculations. By substituting the found solution of the first equation into the modified second equation, after some transformations, we obtain an ordinary first-order differential equation that allows us to determine the first arbitrary function. To determine the second arbitrary function, a compatibility condition is formulated, linking the coefficients and the right-hand sides of the equations. By conducting the appropriate limiting transition, the second arbitrary function is determined based on this condition. Similarly, the system (1) is investigated when the second equation of the system is the main (base) one.

In conclusion, for the considered overdetermined system, a representation of the manifold of solutions has been obtained with a specific relationship between the coefficients of the first and second equations in explicit form. The properties of the obtained solutions have been studied, and problems with initial data K_1, K_2 . have been considered.

Introduction

The theory of systems of partial differential equations with regular coefficients is quite well developed. This theory, associated with the name of Jacobi and other scholars, has been developed for linear homogeneous and non-homogeneous

Date: Date of Submission 28 August, 2025; Date of Acceptance 20 September, 2025, Communicated by Mamadsho Ilolov .

2010 Mathematics Subject Classification. Primary 60H10; Secondary 60H30,60H99.

Key words and phrases. Overdetermined system, variety of solutions, rectangle, internal singular lines, properties of solutions, task with initial data.

systems of first-order partial differential equations with one unknown function of any number of independent variables.

The Frobenius theory for systems in total differentials, both with one and many unknown functions, which is a further development of the Cauchy-Kovalevskaya theory and encompasses certain classes of analytically redefined systems of partial differential equations, dedicated to constructing a manifold of solutions with both regular and singular coefficients, has been further developed in the works of P. Appel [2], L. G. Mikhailov [4], N. Rajabov [5-8], Zh. N. Tasmambetov [9], A. Hasanov [10], F.M. Shamsudinov [11-14] and their students.

The problem of studying differential equations and redefined systems with regular, singular, and super-singular coefficients is addressed in works [1]-[14].

Let D be a rectangle

$$D = \{(x, y) : -a < x < a, 0 < y < a\},$$

$$\Gamma_1 = \{y = 0, -a < x < a\}, \quad \Gamma_2 = \{x = 0, 0 < y < a\}.$$

Further we denote

$$\Gamma_1^0 = \{y = x, 0 \leq x \leq a\}, \quad \Gamma_2^0 = \{y = -x, -a \leq x \leq 0\}.$$

In the field D , we will consider a system of equations of the following form

$$(1) \quad \begin{cases} u_{xy} + a_1(x, y)(x^2 - y^2)^{-m}u_x + b_1(x, y)(x^2 - y^2)^{-n}u_y + \\ + c_1(x, y)(x^2 - y^2)^{-(m+n)}u = f_1(x, y)(x^2 - y^2)^{-(m+n)}, \\ u_y + b_2(x, y)(x^2 - y^2)^{-(m+n)}u = f_2(x, y)(x^2 - y^2)^{-p}, \end{cases}$$

where $a_1(x, y), b_i(x, y), c_1(x, y), f_j(x, y), i = \overline{1, 2}$, - given functions in the field D , $m \geq 2, n \geq 2, p \geq 2, u(x, y)$ - desired function.

Problem statement. Let an overdetermined system of differential equations (1) be given. It is required to find an explicit solution to of the system of differential equations(1) by means of arbitrary constants. Study the behavior of solutions in the neighborhood of internal singular lines and consider problems with initial data.

In the present paper, based on the methods developed in [5], [6] and [8] a overdetermined system of second order partial differential equations with two internal singular lines is investigated.

1. Some facts from matrix theory

Everywhere below we deal with processes, equations, etc., defined on some finite interval $[0, T]$.

We deal with an n -dimensional linear space \mathbb{R}^n , vectors from \mathbb{R}^n and $n \times n$ matrices. Let two $n \times n$ constant matrices L and M be given, where L is singular and M is non-singular. An expression of the form $\lambda L + M$, where λ is a real parameter, is called a matrix pencil. The polynomial $\theta(\lambda) = \det(\lambda L + M)$ is called the characteristic polynomial of the pencil $\lambda L + M$. The pencil is called regular if its characteristic polynomial is not identically zero. If the matrix pencil $\lambda L + M$ is regular, then there exist non-degenerate linear operators P (acting from the left)

and Q (acting from the right) that reduce the matrices L and M to the canonical quasi-diagonal form (see [?]).

In the canonical quasi-diagonal form, having chosen the desired order of the basis vectors, in the matrix PLQ first along the main diagonal there is the $d \times d$ identity matrix, and then along the main diagonal there are Jordan cells with zeros on the diagonal. We denote the $(n - d) \times (n - d)$ matrix with Jordan cells by N .

In PMQ in the lines, corresponding to the unit matrix in L there is a certain non-degenerate matrix J , and in lines, corresponding to Jordan boxes, there is the unit matrix. Thus

$$(2) \quad P(\lambda L + M)Q = \lambda \begin{pmatrix} I_d & 0 \\ 0 & N \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} J & 0 \\ 0 & I_{n-d} \end{pmatrix},$$

A non-degenerate pencil satisfies the rank-degree condition if

$$(3) \quad \text{rank}(L) = \deg(\det(\lambda L + M(t))).$$

If the pencil satisfies the rank-degree condition, then formula (2) takes the form

$$(4) \quad P(\lambda L + M)Q = \lambda \begin{pmatrix} I_d & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} J & 0 \\ 0 & I_{n-d} \end{pmatrix}.$$

where J is non-singular, since B is also a non-singular matrix.

2. Investigation of the system (1) in the case when the first equation of the system is the main one

We will say that in the system of differential equations (1), the first equation is the basic equation if we first find a solution to the first equation and then substitute this solution into the second equation (In the same way, we introduce the concept of basic equation for the second equation).

Let the first equation of the system (1) be the initial equation. Then in this case it will be represented in the form

$$(5) \quad \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial y} + \frac{a_1(x, y)}{(x^2 - y^2)^m} \right) \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} + \frac{b_1(x, y)}{(x^2 - y^2)^n} \right) u = \frac{f_1(x, y) + c_2(x, y)u(x, y)}{(x^2 - y^2)^{m+n}},$$

where

$$(6) \quad c_2(x, y) = -c_1(x, y) + (x^2 - y^2)^{m+n} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{b_1(x, y)}{(x^2 - y^2)^n} \right) + a_1(x, y)b_1(x, y) = 0.$$

In equality (5), introducing a new unknown function $v_1(x, y)$ by the formula

$$(7) \quad \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{b_1(x, y)}{(x^2 - y^2)^n} u = v_1(x, y),$$

reduce the problem to the solution of the following differential equation

$$(8) \quad \frac{\partial v_1}{\partial y} + \frac{a_1(x, y)}{(x^2 - y^2)^m} v_1 = \frac{f_1(x, y) + c_2(x, y)u(x, y)}{(x^2 - y^2)^{m+n}}.$$

In equation (8), considering the right part to be known, we find $v_1(x, y)$ in the form

$$v_1(x, y) = \exp \left[-W_{a_1}^m(x, y) - a_1(x, y)J_{m-1}^{(1)}(x, y) \right] \times$$

$$(9) \quad \times \left(\varphi_1(x) + \int_0^y \frac{f_1(x, s) + c_2(x, s)u(x, s)}{(x^2 - s^2)^{m+n}} \exp \left[W_{a_1}^m(x, s) + a_1(x, x)J_{m-1}^{(1)}(x, s) \right] ds \right),$$

where

$$W_{a_1}^m(x, y) = \int_0^y \frac{a_1(x, s) - a_1(x, x)}{(x^2 - s^2)^m} ds,$$

$$J_{m-1}^{(1)}(x, y) = \frac{y}{2(m-1)x^2(x^2 - y^2)^{m-1}} + \frac{2m-3}{2(m-1)x^2} \int_0^y \frac{ds}{(x^2 - s^2)^{m-1}},$$

Now the solution of equation (7), according to [5], let us write in the form

$$(10) \quad u(x, y) = \exp \left[-W_{b_1}^n(x, y) + b_1(y, y)J_{n-1}^{(2)}(x, y) \right] \times \\ \times \left(\psi_1(y) + \int_0^x v_1(t, y) \exp \left[W_{b_1}^n(t, y) - b_1(y, y)J_{n-1}^{(2)}(t, y) \right] dt \right),$$

where

$$W_{b_1}^n(x, y) = \int_0^x \frac{b_1(t, y) - b_1(y, y)}{(t^2 - y^2)^n} dt,$$

$$J_{n-1}^{(2)}(x, y) = \frac{x}{2(n-1)y^2(x^2 - y^2)^{n-1}} + \frac{2n-3}{2(n-1)y^2} \int_0^x \frac{dt}{(t^2 - y^2)^{n-1}}.$$

Substituting in (10) instead of $v_1(t, y)$ its value from (9), we obtain the integral representation of equation (5) in the form of

$$(11) \quad u(x, y) = \exp \left[-W_{b_1}^n(x, y) + b_1(y, y)J_{n-1}^{(2)}(x, y) \right] \times \\ \times \left\{ \psi_1(y) + \int_0^x \exp \left[W_{b_1}^n(t, y) - b_1(y, y)J_{n-1}^{(2)}(t, y) - W_{a_1}^m(t, y) - a_1(t, t)J_{m-1}^{(1)}(t, y) \right] \times \right. \\ \left. \times \left(\varphi_1(t) + \int_0^y \frac{f_1(t, s) + c_2(t, s)u(t, s)}{(t^2 - s^2)^{m+n}} \exp \left[W_{a_1}^m(t, s) + a_1(t, t)J_{m-1}^{(1)}(t, s) \right] ds \right) dt \right\} \equiv \\ \equiv (K_1(\psi_1(y), \varphi_1(x), f_1(x, y))).$$

Now we write the second equation of the system (1) in the form

$$(12) \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left\{ \exp \left[W_{b_2}^p(x, y) + b_2(x, x)J_{p-1}^{(3)}(x, y) \right] u(x, y) \right\} = \\ = \frac{f_2(x, y)}{(x^2 - y^2)^p} \exp \left[W_{b_2}^p(x, y) + b_2(x, x)J_{p-1}^{(3)}(x, y) \right],$$

where

$$W_{b_2}^p(x, y) = \int_0^y \frac{b_2(x, s) - b_2(x, x)}{(x^2 - s^2)^p} ds,$$

$$J_{p-1}^{(3)}(x, y) = \frac{y}{2(p-1)x^2(x^2 - y^2)^{p-1}} + \frac{2p-3}{2(p-1)x^2} \int_0^y \frac{ds}{(x^2 - s^2)^{p-1}}.$$

By requiring the fulfillment of the condition

$$(13) \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{b_1(x, y)}{(x^2 - y^2)^n} \right) = \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{b_2(x, y)}{(x^2 - y^2)^p} \right) \text{ in } D,$$

and also having differentiated equality (12) by virtue of (13), after some simplifications we obtain the following expression

$$(14) \quad \begin{aligned} \psi_1'(y) + \frac{b_2(0, y)}{(-y^2)^p} \psi_1(y) &= \frac{f_2(x, y)}{(x^2 - y^2)^p} \exp \left[W_{b_1}^n(x, y) - b_1(y, y) J_{n-1}^{(2)}(x, y) \right] - \\ &- \frac{b_2(0, y)}{(-y^2)^p} \int_0^x \exp \left[W_{b_1}^n(t, y) - b_1(y, y) J_{n-1}^{(2)}(t, y) - W_{a_1}^m(t, y) - a_1(t, t) J_{m-1}^{(1)}(t, y) \right] \times \\ &\times \left(\varphi_1(t) + \int_0^y \frac{f_1(t, s) + c_2(t, s)u(t, s)}{(t^2 - s^2)^{m+n}} \exp \left[W_{a_1}^m(t, s) + a_1(t, t) J_{m-1}^{(1)}(t, s) \right] ds \right) dt - \\ &- \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \int_0^x \exp \left[W_{b_1}^n(t, y) - b_1(y, y) J_{n-1}^{(2)}(t, y) - W_{a_1}^m(t, y) - a_1(t, t) J_{m-1}^{(1)}(t, y) \right] \times \\ &\times \left(\varphi_1(t) + \int_0^y \frac{f_1(t, s) + c_2(t, s)u(t, s)}{(t^2 - s^2)^{m+n}} \exp \left[W_{a_1}^m(t, s) + a_1(t, t) J_{m-1}^{(1)}(t, s) \right] ds \right) dt. \end{aligned}$$

From the condition of independence of the left part (14) from the variable x , we obtain

$$(15) \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left\{ \frac{f_2(x, y)}{(x^2 - y^2)^p} \exp \left[W_{b_1}^n(x, y) - b_1(y, y) J_{n-1}^{(2)}(x, y) \right] \right\} - \\ - \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left\{ \exp \left[W_{b_1}^n(t, y) - b_1(y, y) J_{n-1}^{(2)}(t, y) - W_{a_1}^m(t, y) - a_1(t, t) J_{m-1}^{(1)}(t, y) \right] \times \right. \\ \left. \times \left(\varphi_1(x) + \int_0^y \frac{f_1(x, s) + c_2(x, s)u(x, s)}{(t^2 - s^2)^{m+n}} \exp \left[W_{a_1}^m(x, s) + a_1(x, x) J_{m-1}^{(1)}(x, s) \right] ds \right) \right\} = \\ = \frac{b_2(0, y)}{(-y^2)^p} \exp \left[W_{b_1}^n(x, y) - b_1(y, y) J_{n-1}^{(2)}(x, y) - W_{a_1}^m(x, y) - a_1(x, x) J_{m-1}^{(1)}(x, y) \right] \times \\ \times \left(\varphi_1(x) + \int_0^y \frac{f_1(x, s) + c_2(x, s)u(x, s)}{(x^2 - s^2)^{m+n}} \exp \left[W_{a_1}^m(x, s) + a_1(x, x) J_{m-1}^{(1)}(x, s) \right] ds \right). \end{aligned}$$

By transforming the last term of equality (14), according to (15), for determining $\psi_1(y)$ we obtain the following differential equation.

$$(16) \quad \psi_1'(y) + \frac{b_2(0, y)}{(-y^2)^p} \psi_1(y) = \frac{f_2(0, y)}{(-y^2)^p}.$$

When $p = 2k$ - even natural number equation (16) will take form

$$(17) \quad \psi_1'(y) + \frac{b_2(0, y)}{y^{4k}} \psi_1(y) = \frac{f_2(0, y)}{y^{4k}}.$$

The solution of the equation (17) , according to [7], let us write in the form

$$(18) \quad \begin{aligned} \psi_1(y) &= \exp [-W_{b_2}^{4k}(0, y) + b_2(0, 0)W_{4k-1}(y)] \times \\ &\times \left(c_1 + \int_0^y \frac{f_2(0, s)}{s^{4k}} \exp [W_{b_2}^{4k}(0, s) - b_2(0, 0)W_{4k-1}(s)] ds \right) \equiv N_1(c_1, f_2(0, y)), \end{aligned}$$

where

$$W_{b_2}^{4k}(0, y) = \int_0^y \frac{b_2(0, s) - b_2(0, 0)}{s^{4k}} ds, \quad W_{4k-1} = \frac{1}{(4k - 1)y^{4k-1}},$$

c_1 - an arbitrary constant.

In equality (15) , performing the operation of differentiation, after simplification we obtain

$$(19) \quad \begin{aligned} &((x^2 - y^2)^{m+n}b_2(x, y) - (x^2 - y^2)^{p+n}a_1(x, y)) \times \\ &\quad \times \exp [-W_{a_1}^m(x, y) - a_1(x, x)J_{m-1}^{(1)}(x, y)] \times \\ &\times \left(\varphi_1(x) + \int_0^y \frac{f_1(x, s) + c_2(x, s)u(x, s)}{(x^2 - s^2)^{m+n}} \exp [W_{a_1}^m(x, s) + a_1(x, x)J_{m-1}^{(1)}(x, s)] ds \right) + \\ &\quad + (x^2 - y^2)^p f_1(x, y) = (x^2 - y^2)^{m+n+p} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{f_2(x, y)}{(x^2 - y^2)^p} \right) + \\ &\quad + (x^2 - y^2)^m b_1(x, y) f_2(x, y) \text{ in } D. \end{aligned}$$

In equality (19) at $y \rightarrow 0$ in the case $c_2(x, y) = 0$ passing to the limit we define $\varphi_1(x)$ in the form

$$(20) \quad \begin{aligned} \varphi_1(x) &= \frac{1}{x^{2(m+n)}b_1(x, 0) - x^{2(p+n)}a_1(x, 0)} \times \\ &\times \left[x^{2(m+n+p)} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{f_2(x, y)}{(x^2 - y^2)^p} \right)_{y=0} + x^{2m}b_1(x, 0)f_2(x, 0) - x^{2p}f_1(x, 0) \right] \equiv \\ &\equiv G_1(x) (a_1(x, 0) \neq b_2(x, 0)). \end{aligned}$$

So, the following theorem is proved.

Theorem 2.1. *Let the coefficients and right-hand sides of the system of equations (1) satisfy the following conditions*

- (1) $b_1(x, y) \in C_y^1(\bar{D})$, $b_2(x, y) \in C_x^1(\bar{D})$, $f_2(x, y) \in C_x^1(\bar{D})$, $a_1(x, y)$, $c_1(x, y)$, $f_1(x, y) \in C(\bar{D})$;
- (2) $c_1(x, y) = (x^2 - y^2)^{m+n} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{b_1(x, y)}{(x^2 - y^2)^n} \right) + a_1(x, y)b_1(x, y)$;
- (3) $b_1(y, y) > 0$, $a_1(x, x) > 0$, $b_2(y, y) > 0$;
- (4) $b_1(x, y) - b_1(y, y) = o((x - y)^{\beta_1})$, $\beta_1 > n - 1$ in the neighborhood Γ_1^0 ,
 $b_1(x, y) - b_1(y, y) = o((x + y)^{\beta_2})$, $\beta_2 > n - 1$ in the neighborhood Γ_2^0 ,
 $a_1(x, y) - a_1(x, x) = o((x - y)^{\alpha_1})$, $\alpha_1 > m - 1$ in the neighborhood Γ_1^0 ,
 $a_1(x, y) - a_1(x, x) = o((x + y)^{\alpha_2})$, $\alpha_2 > m - 2$ in the neighborhood Γ_2^0 ,
 $|b_2(0, y) - b_2(0, 0)| \leq H_1 y^{\mu_1}$, $H_1 = \text{const}$, $\mu_1 > 4k - 1$;
- (5) a) $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{b_1(x, y)}{(x^2 - y^2)^n} \right) = \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{b_2(x, y)}{(x^2 - y^2)^p} \right)$ in D ,
 b) $((x^2 - y^2)^{m+n} b_2(x, y) - (x^2 - y^2)^{p+n} a_1(x, y)) \times$
 $\times \exp \left[-W_{a_1}^m(x, y) - a_1(x, x) J_{m-1}^{(1)}(x, y) \right] \times$
 $\times \left(\varphi_1(x) + \int_0^y \frac{f_1(x, s)}{(x^2 - s^2)^{m+n}} \exp \left[W_{a_1}^m(x, s) + a_1(x, x) J_{m-1}^{(1)}(x, s) \right] ds \right) +$
 $+ (x^2 - y^2)^p f_1(x, y) = (x^2 - y^2)^{m+n+p} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{f_2(x, y)}{(x^2 - y^2)^p} \right) +$
 $+ (x^2 - y^2)^m b_1(x, y) f_2(x, y)$ in D ;
- (6) $f_1(x, y) = o \left(\exp \left[-a_1(x, x) J_{m-1}^{(1)}(x, y) \right] (x - y)^{\lambda_1} \right)$, $\lambda_1 > m+n-1$ in the neighborhood Γ_1^0 ,
 $f_1(x, y) = o \left(\exp \left[-a_1(x, x) J_{m-1}^{(1)}(x, y) \right] (x + y)^{\lambda_2} \right)$, $\lambda_2 > m+n-1$ in the neighborhood Γ_2^0 ,
 $f_2(0, y) = o((y)^{\mu_1})$, $\mu_1 > 4k - 1$.

Then any solution of the system of equations (1) from the class $C^2(D \setminus (\Gamma_1^0 \cup \Gamma_2^0))$ is representable as (11), when $c_2(x, y) = 0$, (18) and (20), where c_1 - an arbitrary constant.

The obtained solution has the properties:

1°. If $x \rightarrow 0$, then

$$u(0, y) = \psi_1(y).$$

2°. If $x \rightarrow 0$ and $y \rightarrow 0$, then

$$\lim_{y \rightarrow 0} \left\{ \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} u(x, y) \right\} = O(\exp[b_2(0, 0)W_{4k-1}(y)]).$$

3°.

$$\lim_{y \rightarrow 0} \left\{ \exp[-b_2(0, 0)W_{4k-1}(y)] \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} u(x, y) \right\} = c_1.$$

4°. If $y \rightarrow 0$ and $x \neq 0$, then

$$u(x, y) = O \left(\exp \left[b_1(y, y) J_{n-1}^{(2)}(x, y) \right] \right).$$

Remark 1. Similar statements for the system of equations (1) are obtained, when $p = 2k - 1 (k = 1, 2, 3, \dots)$.

3. Study of the system (1) in the case when the second equation of the system is initial

Let the second equation of the system (1) be the principal equation. Then by above the following theorem is proved

Theorem 3.1. *Let the coefficients and right-hand sides of the system of equations (1) satisfy the following conditions*

- (1) $b_1(x, y) \in C_y^1(\overline{D})$, $b_2(x, y) \in C_x^1(\overline{D})$, $f_2(x, y) \in C_x^1(\overline{D})$, $a_1(x, y)$, $c_1(x, y)$, $f_1(x, y) \in C(\overline{D})$;
- (2) $c_2(x, y) = -c_1(x, y) + (x^2 - y^2)^{m+n} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{b_1(x, y)}{(x^2 - y^2)^n} \right) + a_1(x, y)b_1(x, y) \neq 0$;
- (3) $b_2(x, x) < 0, B_1(0, 0) > 0$;
- (4) $b_2(x, y) - b_2(x, x) = o((x - y)^{\mu_1})$, $\mu_1 > p - 1$ in the neighborhood Γ_1^0 ,
 $b_2(x, y) - b_2(x, x) = o((x + y)^{\mu_2})$, $\mu_2 > n - 1$ in the neighborhood Γ_2^0 ,
 $|B_1(x, 0) - B_1(0, 0)| \leq H_1 y^{\mu_3}$, $H_1 = \text{const}$, $\mu_3 > 2(m + n + p) - 1$;
- (5) a) $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{b_2(x, y)}{(x^2 - y^2)^p} \right) = \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{b_1(x, y)}{(x^2 - y^2)^n} \right)$ in D ,
 b) $(x^2 - y^2)^{m+n+p} \left((x^2 - y^2)^{-p} b_2(x, y) - (x^2 - y^2)^{-m} a_1(x, y) \right) \times$
 $\times \exp \left[-W_{a_1}^m(x, y) - a_1(x, x) J_{m-1}^{(1)}(x, y) \right] \times$
 $\times \left(\varphi_1(x) + \int_0^y \frac{f_1(x, s) + c_2(x, s) K_2(\varphi_2(x), f_2(x, y))}{(x^2 - s^2)^{m+n}} \exp \left[W_{a_1}^m(x, s) + a_1(x, x) J_{m-1}^{(1)}(x, s) \right] ds \right) +$
 $+ (x^2 - y^2)^p f_1(x, y) + (x^2 - y^2)^p c_2(x, y) K_2(\varphi_2(x), f_2(x, y)) =$
 $= (x^2 - y^2)^m b_1(x, y) f_2(x, y) + (x^2 - y^2)^{m+n+p} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{f_2(x, y)}{(x^2 - y^2)^p} \right)$ in D ;
- (6) $f_2(x, y) = o \left(\exp \left[-b_2(x, x) J_{p-1}^{(3)}(x, y) \right] (x - y)^{\lambda_1} \right)$, $\lambda_1 > p - 1$ in the neighborhood Γ_1^0 ,
 $f_2(x, y) = o \left(\exp \left[-b_2(x, x) J_{p-1}^{(3)}(x, y) \right] (x + y)^{\lambda_2} \right)$, $\lambda_2 > p - 1$ in the neighborhood Γ_2^0 ,
 $F_1(x) = o(x^{\lambda_3})$, $\lambda_3 > 2(m + n + p) - 1$.

Then any solution of the system of equations (1) from the class $C^2(D \setminus (\Gamma_0^1 \cup \Gamma_0^2))$ is representable as

$$(21) \quad u(x, y) = \exp \left[-W_{b_2}^p(x, y) - b_2(x, x) J_{p-1}^{(1)}(x, y) \right] \times$$

$$\times \left(\varphi_2(x) + \int_0^y \frac{f_2(x, s)}{(x^2 - s^2)^p} \exp \left[W_{b_2}^p(x, s) + b_2(x, x) J_{p-1}^{(1)}(x, s) \right] ds \right) \equiv$$

$$\equiv K_2((\varphi_2(x), f_2(x, y))),$$

where

$$\varphi_2(x) = \exp \left[-W_{B_1}^{2(m+n+p)}(x, 0) + B_1(0, 0) W_{2(m+n+p)-1}(x) \right] \times$$

$$(22) \quad \times \left(c_2 + \int_0^x \frac{F_1(t)}{t^{2(m+n+p)}} \exp \left[W_{B_1}^{2(m+n+p)}(t, 0) - B_1(0, 0)W_{2(m+n+p)-1}(t) \right] dt \right) \equiv \\ \equiv N_2(c_2, F_1(x)),$$

$$B_1(x, 0) = x^{2(m+n)}b_1(x, 0) + c_2(x, 0), \\ F_1(x) = \frac{1}{x^{-2p}b_2(x, 0) - x^{-2m}a_1(x, 0)} \times \\ \times \left[x^{2(m+n+p)} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{f_2(x, y)}{(x^2 - y^2)^p} \right)_{y=0} + x^{2m}b_1(x, 0)f_2(x, 0) - x^{2p}f_1(x, 0) \right] \equiv \\ \equiv G_1(x) \quad (a_1(x, 0) \neq b_2(x, 0)), \\ W_{B_1}^{2(m+n+p)}(x, 0) = \int_0^x \frac{B_1(t, 0) - B_1(0, 0)}{t^{2(m+n+p)}} dt, \\ W_{2(m+n+p)-1}(x) = \frac{1}{(2(m+n+p) - 1)x^{2(m+n+p)-1}},$$

c_2 – is an arbitrary constant.

The solution obtained has the properties:

1°. If $y \rightarrow 0$, then

$$u(x, 0) = \varphi_2(x).$$

2°. If $y \rightarrow 0$ and $x \rightarrow 0$, then

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \left\{ \lim_{y \rightarrow 0} u(x, y) \right\} = O \left(\exp[B_1(0, 0)W_{2(m+n+p)-1}(x)] \right).$$

3°.

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \left\{ \exp[-B_1(0, 0)W_{2(m+n+p)-1}(x)] \lim_{y \rightarrow 0} u(x, y) \right\} = c_2.$$

4°. If $x \rightarrow 0$ and $y \neq 0$, then

$$u(x, y) = O \left(\exp \left[-b_2(x, x)J_{p-1}^{(3)}(x, y) \right] \right).$$

The obtained integral representations of solutions and its properties make it possible for the system of equations (1) to set and solve the following problems with initial data.

Problem K_1 . It is required to find a solution of the system of equations (1) from the class $C^2(D \setminus (\Gamma_0^1 \cup \Gamma_0^2))$ by the initial condition

$$\lim_{y \rightarrow 0} \left\{ \exp[-b_2(0, 0)W_{4k-1}(y)] \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} u(x, y) \right\} = q_1,$$

where q_1 – is a given known constant number.

Problem K_2 . It is required to find the solution of the system of equations (1) from the class $C^2(D \setminus (\Gamma_0^1 \cup \Gamma_0^2))$ by the initial condition

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \left\{ \exp[-B_1(0, 0)W_{2(m+n+p)-1}(x)] \lim_{y \rightarrow 0} u(x, y) \right\} = q_2,$$

where q_2 is a given known constant number.

Solution of problem K_1 . To solve this problem, we use the integral representation of the solutions of (8) at $c_2(x, y) = 0$, (15), (17), the condition of problem K_1 and obtain that $c_1 = q_1$.

Theorem 3. *Let all conditions of theorem 1 be satisfied, then the single solution of problem K_1 is represented in the form (8) at $c_2(x, y) = 0$, (15), (17), where $c_1 = q_1$.*

Solution of problem K_2 . To solve this problem, we use the integral representation of the solutions of (18), (19), the condition of problem K_2 and obtain that $c_2 = q_2$.

Theorem 4. *Let all conditions of theorem 2 be satisfied, then the single solution of problem K_2 is represented in the form (18), (19), where $c_2 = q_2$.*

References

- [1] Nelson E.: Derivation of the Schrödinger equation from Newtonian mechanics. *Phys. Reviews*, 1966, Vol. 150, No. 4, 1079 – 1085
- [2] Wilczynski E.J. Projective Differential Geometry of Curves and Ruled Sur-faces. -Zeip. Zig; Leubner, 1906. – 120 p.
- [3] Appel P. Fonctons hypergeometriges of hyperspheriges Polynomes d’Hermite. – Paris: GauthierVillars. – 1926. – 434 s.
- [4] Stepanov V.V. Course of differential equations.— M.: Fizmatgiz,1959.— 468p. (in Russian).
- [5] Mikhailov L.G. Some overdetermined systems of partial derivative equations with two unknown functions. - Dushanbe: ed. Donish, 1986. — 115p. (in Russian).
- [6] Rajabov N. Integral representations and boundary value problems for some differential equations with singular line or singular surfaces. Dushanbe: iz-vo TSU, 1985. — 145p. (in Russian).
- [7] Rajabov N. Introduction to the theory of partial differential equations with supersingular coefficients. — Dushanbe. ed. TSU, 1992. — 236p. (in Russian).
- [8] Rajabov N. Introdaction to ordinary differential equations with super–singular coefficients. Dushanbe, 1998. — 160p.
- [9] Rajabov N., Mahamed Elsayed Abdel Aal. Overdetermined second order linear system with singular and supersingular lines. - Lap Lambert Academic Publishing, Germany, 2011. — 234p. (in Russian).
- [10] Tasmambetov J. N. Construction of normal and normal-regular solutions of special systems of partial differential equations of second order. — Aktobe: 2015. — 463 p. (in Russian).
- [11] Hasanov A.H. Fundamental solutions of ganeralized biaxially symmetric Helmholtz equation. *Complex Variables and Elliptic Equations*. – Vol. 52, N8 , 2007 . – pp. 673-683.
- [12] Shamsuddinov F. M. About one overdetermined system of second order differential equations with singular point // *Vestnik. Volgogr. Gos. un-ta. Ser. Mat. Phys.* 2016, No. 6(37). – P. 99 – 107. (in Russian).
- [13] Shamsudinov F. M. On the study of a class of second-order hyperbolic equations and related redefined systems of differential equations with singular and super-singular points. : thesis ... for the degree of Doctor of Physical and Mathematical Sciences: 010102: defended on 25.12.19: approved on 25.09.20 / Shamsudinov Faizullo Mamadullayevich. - D., 2019. - 355 p. - Bibliography: pp. 338 - 355.
- [14] Shamsuddinov F. M. Integral representations of solutions for one overdetermined system of second order differential equations with strong singularity // *Bulletin of the Tajik National University. Series of natural sciences*. – 2015.– No 1/4(168). – P.37-42. (in Russian).
- [15] Shamsuddinov F. M. Integral representations of solutions for one overdetermined second-order system with singular point // *Bulletin of the Tajik National University. Series of natural sciences*. – 2015.– No 1/1(156). – P. 60 - 65. (in Russian).

ON A CLASS OVERDETERMINED SYSTEMS OF ...

SHAMSUDINOV FAYZULLO MAMADULLOEVICH, BOKHTAR STATE UNIVERSITY NAMED AFTER NOSIR KHUSRAV, TAJIKISTAN

Email address: faizullo100@yahoo.com

VALIEV RUZIBOY SANGIMURODOVICH, BOKHTAR STATE UNIVERSITY NAMED AFTER NOSIR KHUSRAV, TAJIKISTAN

Email address: ruziboivaliev@gmail.com

DUNYA ABDALHAMEED HASAN, DEPARTMENT OF PHYSICS , COLLEGE OF EDUCATION , UNIVERSITY OF SAMARRA, IRAQ

Email address: dunya.7364@gmail.com